

Chemical Constituents of *Hydrangea vestita* and *Hydrangea heteromalla*

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THE genus *Hydrangea* belonging to the family Saxifragaceae comprises about 33 species, mainly native to Java, temperate Himalayas, Japan, Eastern North America and Western South America.¹ The isolation and characterization of the crystalline constituents of two uninvestigated species of this genus, *H. vestita* Wall and *H. heteromalla* Don Prodr., growing in the temperate Himalayas from Britan to Kumaon (altitude 2500-3000 m), frequently in Khasia mountains (1500-2000 m)¹ and collected from Darjiling district are reported here. Both these plants are devoid of any alkaloid.

The whole plant of *H. vestita* afforded from the CHCl_3 extract two major phenolic coumarins, umbelliferone (I) (yield 1.9%) and daphnetin-8-methyl ether (II) (0.019%) and one minor phenolic coumarin, fraxetin (III) (0.026%) while the light petrol extract afforded only (II) (0.15%). (I) and (II) were reported earlier from *H. macrophylla*.² The leaves of *H. heteromalla* yielded ursolic acid (IV) (0.032%) and sitosterol (0.02%) from the light petrol extract while the CHCl_3 extract did not afford any solid. The identity of each compound as indicated by their spectral data (IR, PMR and MS) was established by direct comparison (m.p., co-TLC, superimposable IR) with the respective authentic sample available in this laboratory and in some cases through the preparation of characteristic derivatives.

Experimental

Extraction: Air-dried and milled whole plant (800 g) of *H. vestita* and leaves (400 g) of *H. heteromalla* were exhaustively extracted in turn with light petrol (60°-80°) and CHCl_3 in a Soxhlet apparatus for 40 hr. The extract concentrates, found to be devoid of any basic component, were separately chromatographed over silica gel and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity.

***H. vestita*, daphnetin-8-methyl ether:** The deep brown residue (26 g) of the petrol extract on repeated chromatography afforded from CHCl_3 eluate fractions daphnetin-8-methyl ether, crystallizing from CH_2Cl_2 in transparent needles, m.p. 155°-56° (120 mg), the

IR, PMR and MS data of which were already reported.³ The acetate, prepared by the $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$ method, separated from CH_2Cl_2 as colourless needles, m.p. 135°-36° and the methyl ether formed by CH_2N_2 treatment crystallized from CHCl_3 in needles, m.p. 119°-20°.

Umbelliferone (I) and fraxetin (III): The CHCl_3 extract concentrate on cooling afforded a solid residue (3 g) which upon repeated chromatography yielded from $\text{CHCl}_3 : \text{M.OH}$ (19:1) eluates umbelliferone, crystallizing from CH_3COCH_3 in colourless needles, m.p. 225° (0.70 g); acetyl derivative, m.p. 140° ($\text{CHCl}_3\text{-M.OH}$). The yellow gummy residue (5 g) from the mother liquor of the CHCl_3 extract on repeated chromatography gave further amounts of daphnetin-8-methyl ether (0.15 g) from CHCl_3 eluates and umbelliferone (0.8 g) from $\text{CHCl}_3\text{:M.OH}$ (19:1) eluates. The residue from $\text{CHCl}_3 : \text{M.OH}$ (9:1) eluates was rechromatographed to afford fraxetin, crystallizing from CH_3COCH_3 in colourless needles, m.p. 228° (0.05 g); PMR (100 MHz, δ): 6.21 and 7.88d (AB system, J 10Hz, H-3 and H-4), 6.79 s(H-5) and 3.82 s(OMe); MS: intense peaks at m/e 208 (100% M^+), 193 (88, $\text{M}^+ - \text{M}_1$, characteristics of 6-OMe coumarins)⁴, 180 (27, $\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}$), 165 (24, m/e 193-CO), 137 (29, m/e 165-CO), 109 (31, m/e 137-CO); acetate, m.p. 192-93°; methyl ether, m.p. 103-04° CHCl_3 -petrol).

***H. heteromalla*, sitosterol and ursolic acid:** The residue (13 g) from the light petrol extract was chromatographed and the residue from $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 : \text{CHCl}_3$ (1:1) eluates upon rechromatography two times yielded sitosterol (0.105 g), m.p. 138° ($\text{CHCl}_3\text{-M.OH}$), $[\alpha]_D -45^\circ$ (CHCl_3), acetate, m.p. 134°. The residue obtained from CHCl_3 eluates of the main chromatogram was purified by several rechromatographies and crystallizations from absolute EtOH to yield ursolic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 291° (0.13 g), $[\alpha]_D +71^\circ$ (CHCl_3); R_f 0.4, silica gel, $\text{CHCl}_3 : \text{M.OH}$ (9:1); it showed positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for triterpene and formed a mono acetate, m.p. 291°-292° (petrol - CHCl_3) which in turn formed a mono-methyl ester, m.p. 249° (petrol - CH_3OH) on treatment with CH_2N_2 .

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